

European network to promote grazing and to support grazing-based farms on their economic and ecologic performances as well as on animal welfare

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1 Introduction

The Grazing4Agroecology (G4AE) project aims to empower farmers and agricultural advisors by enhancing their skills in video creation and storytelling through innovative digital training. As part of this initiative, we are excited to present the "Grazing Farm and Video Awards", a key deliverable designed to celebrate excellence in sustainable grazing practices.

This dual-focused deliverable encompasses two main components: the online EU video-training webinars and the G4AE farm competition. The video-training webinars were conducted in English, under the guidance of an external specialist, helping participants (Facilitator Agents) harness the power of smartphones and free software for effective video production. Additionally, national storytelling seminars were organized by the FAs to facilitate learning in the native languages of participating member states, further enriching the experience for farmers and advisors alike.

In conjunction with these training efforts, the G4AE farm competition spotlighted innovative grazing practices and performance metrics within agroecological frameworks. The competition's rules, selection criteria, judging panel, and evaluation process were established by month 12 of the project in all partners' countries. The competition recognizes farmers who are optimizing grazing to improve the five principles of agroecology within their animal production systems.

1. Adopting management practices that aim to improve animal health
2. Reducing the inputs required for production
3. Reducing pollution by optimizing the biogeochemical functioning of farming systems
4. Enhancing diversity within animal production systems to strengthen their resilience
5. Preserving biodiversity in agro-ecosystems by adapting management practices

As the grazing season begins in year two, the competition was launched in each member state, culminating in the recognition of national winners by the end of the grazing season. A comprehensive report detailing the top three winners from each country is prepared here, while the overall first prize winner will be awarded during the Grazing4AgroEcology General Partner Assembly (GPA) in Ireland (April 2025).

The final result of this initiative will not only be the recognition of farming excellence through the awards but also the celebration of outstanding video contributions that capture the spirit of innovation in grazing for agroecology. These best national videos will be featured on our project website, highlighting the ongoing commitment to promote sustainable agricultural practices and bring people together across Europe.

2. Grazing4Agroecology France Awards

G4AE Grazing farm award description

The "Parie sur ta prairie" ("Bet on your grassland") award was created in 2021 by a group of farmers from the Pays de la Loire region as part of the CLIMATVEG project. The goal of this competition is to highlight the practices used by farmers to adapt their sown grasslands to climate change.

The 2024 edition of the contest was organized within the framework of the European Grazing4Agroecology project in the Brittany region. It was open to all Breton farmers with a sown grassland between 4 and 8 years old. This year, 10 dairy and beef farmers from Finistère and Morbihan participated. Their grasslands were assessed in autumn 2024 by a jury composed of farmers (Tangi Tréhen, Cédric Tymen and Alain Normant) and forage advisors from the Brittany Chamber of Agriculture (Dimitri Benoit and Benoit Possémé).

The jury evaluated the coherence between the sown species and varieties, the soil and climate conditions of the plot, and the farmer's objectives for the field. Through detailed observation, they also assessed the quality of the existing flora composition and the quality of grazing infrastructure, such as the presence of trees and hedgerows, plot accessibility, and the condition of paths and fences.

A key focus of the evaluation was the overall coherence between the farmer's objectives and the practices adopted to maintain the productive potential and species diversity of the grassland despite climatic challenges. After evaluating each grassland individually, the three best grasslands were re-assessed by a regional jury composed of two forage advisors from the Brittany Chamber of Agriculture and a grassland expert from the French Livestock Institute. This regional jury determined the winners of the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd prizes.

The first-place winner, Kévin Hélibert, was awarded a study trip to Ireland along with €500, funded by the Végépolys Valley competitiveness cluster. The second- and third-place winners also received €500 each.

1st prize winner // Kévin Hélibert // // Improving grazing infrastructures //

Kévin owns an organic dairy farm in northwest Brittany (Plabennec), consisting of approximately 50 dairy cows, each producing 6,500 liters per lactation. The farm spans 43 hectares, with plots consolidated into a single site, and is primarily sown with meadows. Kevin pays close attention to his grazing infrastructure, including the water system, fences, and roadway network. He has also planted tree lines between paddocks, driven by environmental concerns and a desire to enhance his cows' welfare.

The farm benefits from high-quality soils and a mild climate, with 1,300 mm of annual rainfall and average temperatures ranging from 7 to 15°C, enabling year-round grazing on high-yield pastures. Clover plays a key role in nitrogen supply for the fields. Kevin groups all calvings between September and November to ensure sufficient grass quality and quantity when the cows' needs are highest. He believes this approach is more secure than spring calving, as climate change has made spring grass growth increasingly erratic, while autumn growth has proven more stable and abundant.

2nd prize winner //Kévin Tymen// //Legumes in swards//

Kévin Tymen runs an organic farm in the southwest of Brittany. He cultivates around 65 hectares of grass to feed his 115 dairy cows, which produce approximately 3,200 liters per lactation. He places a strong emphasis on excellent grazing management and infrastructure. To improve pasture quality and provide nitrogen, he incorporates clover in his grasslands.

The mild climate—receiving 1,300 mm of rainfall per year with average temperatures ranging from 7 to 17°C—and the high soil quality ensure consistent grass growth in spring without any risk of drought. For this reason, he has grouped all his calvings between early February and late March. The calves are raised outdoors in groups almost from birth.

During winter, all dry cows are managed using the bale-grazing technique. This approach helps Kévin reduce hay consumption and fuel use, as it minimizes the need for manure spreading and forage transportation.

3rd prize winner // Jean-Louis Kerdelhue // Grass and legumes lays//

Jean-Louis Kerdelhue runs a farm in the southern coastal region of Brittany. He raises 30 suckler cows, selling the male calves to fattening farms while fattening the heifers on-site and selling the meat directly to customers.

He owns 75 hectares of meadows sown with species-rich seed mixes, 30 hectares of pure or mixed forage legumes (alfalfa and red clover), 20 hectares of winter crops—mainly wheat to ensure his straw supply—and 20 hectares of spring crops, primarily grain corn. His goal is to maximize farm self-sufficiency and minimize external inputs for both crops and livestock. He relies on forage legumes to meet his cattle's protein needs and corn to ensure their energy supply.

As his farm is in an area increasingly affected by drought due to climate change, he places great importance on securing his forage resources. To achieve this, he maintains slightly more land than strictly necessary to feed his cattle. This strategy also allows him to manage his land extensively, in line with his ecological values.

G4AE storytelling video award description

The storytelling seminar was held on June 7, 2023, organized by Soline Schetelat (IDELE) and Jean-Marc Seuret (Chambre d'Agriculture de Bretagne) (see the picture below). The 15 participants were forage, dairy cattle, and beef cattle advisors from the Chambre d'Agriculture de Bretagne. The objective of this training was to equip advisors with the skills needed to film testimonial videos of farmers, a task they are required to perform in various projects. First, we reviewed the process of designing the video script: to write a high-quality synopsis, it is essential to define the key messages to be conveyed and determine the video's

duration. Then, a storyboard should be drafted to plan the questions to ask the farmer and the shots to be captured. Next, we discussed the video equipment to be used (smartphone, microphone, tripod) and the free editing software available. Several farm applications were received in the G4AE storytelling video competition that are currently under assessment. Results will be available on the G4AE website (<https://grazing4agroecology.eu/innovations/infothek-video/>).

3. Grazing4Agroecology Germany Awards

G4AE Grazing farm award description

The Grazing Award was carried out in autumn 2024 via an online questionnaire. Grazing farms from Germany were able to register for the award from 10 September to 15 November 2024. A total of 24 dairy cattle and suckler cow farms took part in the competition. The evaluation of the submissions was completed on 17 December 2024. The multi-stage evaluation process is divided into three parts.

▼ Betriebsform

*** Welches ist Ihr wichtigster Betriebszweig?**

Ackerbau

Grünlandbewirtschaftung Milch/Fleisch

Grünlandbewirtschaftung Landschaftspflege (Schnittwiesen/gezielte Pflege mittels Beweidung)

Tourismus

Andere

*** Welche weiteren Betriebszweige führen Sie?**

Ackerbau

Grünlandbewirtschaftung Milch/Fleisch

Grünlandbewirtschaftung Landschaftspflege (Schnittwiesen/gezielte Pflege mittels Beweidung)

Direktvermarktung

Figure 1: Questions for Award, published on KoboToolBox

1. After reviewing the submissions, a pre-selection of the best six companies was made using a points system. A maximum of 3 or 5 points could be awarded per subpillar.
 - (1) Heiko Stelling 20,5 Punkte
 - (2) Swen Ahlers 20,5 Punkte
 - (3) Christian Grensemann 20 Punkte
 - (4) Moritz Morgenstern 20,5 Punkte
 - (5) Syds-Jan Boersma 19 Punkte
 - (6) Heiko Müller 19,5 Punkte
2. In the next evaluation step, the TOP6 dairy and suckler cow farms were interviewed by telephone. In follow-up interviews, the participants were asked the same questions and results were documented. Among other things, the farms were asked for an income-relevant assessment of the farm sectors in order to be able to categorise the resilience and diversity of the farm sectors. In addition, specific questions were asked about pasture management during the critical phases (pre-grazing period, protein supplementation during summer), characteristics of land, grassland management and the farm's potential for adaptation during the past 5 years.
3. Assessment of the national AKIS members during the third AKIS meeting on December 17th, 2024. All AKIS members acted as a jury. At the beginning, all participants received information about the six best companies. In a subsequent two-way discussion, the companies were to be discussed objectively. In the third step, all AKIS members gave a ranking from 1 to 3. This resulted in the following ranking:

1st prize winner //Heiko Stelling// //From zero-grazing to full-day grazing //

Heiko Stelling’s dairy farm is in Bremervörde, Lower-Saxony on wetlands and he operates under conventional farming practices. The farm has permanent grassland as grazing platform and arable land on mineral soils, primarily cultivating maize and other forage crops.

In addition to dairy production, the farm has established direct marketing channels for its products, including cheese and free-range eggs. A significant restructuring of the farm took place in 2021, which included the transition to full-day grazing with Holstein Friesian (HF) and crossbred animals.

The farm has implemented a seasonal calving system to optimize production efficiency. It has transitioned from a “jogging” grazing system to full-day grazing without supplementary roughage from April to August and ensuring that the animals have access to high-quality pasture.

Water infrastructure has been established to provide water supply for the livestock on pasture. Heiko measures once a week the grass growth by using a digital plate meter and a pasture management decision-support tool (AgriNet), allowing for precise monitoring of pasture conditions.

Additionally, a rotational grazing system has been implemented to increase fresh-grass uptake and enhance animal welfare and health.

2nd prize winner //Syds-Jan Boersma// //Topping during drought //

Syds-Jan's farm manages grassland on marsh and clay soils and milks 170 Jersey cows. As an intensive full-grazing farm, his aim is not only to further reduce the costs of buying in feed, but also to utilise the pasture as efficiently as possible as the farm's own high-quality feed source.

As a grazing strategy, they top the grass from June to August. Topping means to cut the upper part of the grass just before it goes into seedhead. The cut part is left, and the plot is grazed after a short wilting of the cut. This has two advantages: Firstly, the grass growth is stimulated again so that the animals can graze a plot with high forage quality more quickly. Secondly, the slight drying out of the cut results in higher palatability and feed intake by the animals, which is reflected in slightly higher productivity. Topping is carried out from June to August until the grass no longer goes into seedhead. The time of cutting and the weather must be right for topping. The grass should not already be too high, otherwise the animals will no longer eat the lower part and there will be too much residue. The grass must also be dry. The diagram below illustrates the practice using a rotational grazing system as an example:

3rd prize winner //Moritz Morgenstern// //Individual sales channel //

Moritz Morgenstern has a family-owned organic dairy farm with 170 red dairy cows with milk production of 6,500 kg per cow. The Red cows is a breed threatened by extinction; Moritz receives subsidies for preserving the breed. The farm has 156 hectares of arable land, managed under a wide 7-field crop rotation system, which promotes soil health and sustainability.

In addition to dairy production, the farm has nature conservation grassland, contributing to biodiversity and environmental programmes. The farm sells most of the milk to an organic processor and approx. 30% is sold in direct marketing. The dynamic organic produced milk is sold directly to a regional retailer (Edeka) through a marketing company he established with four other farms (Demeter). They supply according to the strict criteria of the label "Nordfrische Bauernmilch".

G4AE storytelling video award description

The national Storytelling Seminar took place online on February 12th, 2025, aiming to reach a broad audience of farmers and young farmers interested in sharing their work in grazing through video content. The goal is to promote dialogue between agriculture and society. 35 participants participated the seminar, including two school classes from the agricultural sector, who have been specifically invited.

Organized by the Grünlandzentrum, the seminar introduced key aspects of video production, focusing on storytelling, camera techniques, and the 5-shot method. The Dairy Association of Lower Saxony (Landesvereinigung der Milchwirtschaft Niedersachsen), known for its popular MyKuhTube channel (professional videos from farms), has provided practical advice on planning and creating short videos for social media. Topics include technical equipment, preparation (theme, core message, structure, location), and effective communication for target audiences.

Additionally, farmer Amos Venema, who regularly shares agricultural content on social media and on the MyKuhTube channel, offered tips and insights from his experience. Participants also received recommendations for free editing software and links to further information on this topic.

Grazing 4 AgroEcology meets

VIDEO-WORKSHOP

FÜR LANDWIRTTINNEN & LANDWIRTE

BONUS
Wer im Anschluss ein eigenes Video dreht, kann an unserem Video-Award teilnehmen.

12. Februar **10-11.30 Uhr**

 Online über Zoom (ohne Anmeldung)

AUF DEM PROGRAMM

- Grundlagen des Videodrehens und Storytellings
- Einblicke aus der Praxis von MyKuhTube
- Tipps & Tricks von Landwirt & KuhTuber Amos Venema

DAS ZIEL

Den Austausch zwischen Landwirtschaft und Gesellschaft fördern – nehmt die Menschen mit und zeigt ihnen, was ihr tagtäglich tut. Ihr habt so viele Themen, die es sich lohnt zu kommunizieren!

Following the seminar, participants will be encouraged to apply their knowledge by creating their own grazing-themed videos by April 16th, 2025. The school classes will integrate this task into their curriculum, while other participants can voluntarily submit their videos. The best video, evaluated based on storytelling criteria, will win the Video Award, be featured on the Grazing4AgroEcology website, and be showcased at the next GPA event in Ireland on April 29th, 2025.

4. Grazing4Agroecology Ireland Awards

G4AE Grazing farm award description

The G4AC Sustainable Grassland Farmer of the Year Competition was an initiative open to all livestock farmers based in the Republic of Ireland. To begin the process, preliminary judging took place, focusing on the information provided in the application form, alongside data sourced from organizations such as Teagasc, Bord Bia, and the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine systems. Following this initial assessment, the final judging phase involved a panel of five judges visiting the shortlisted farms to observe firsthand the practices being implemented.

The application form was open for applicants from July to September and the winner was chosen in October. The competition is supported by the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine, Teagasc, Allied Irish Banks, Farmer Business Development, Grassland Agro and the Irish Farmers Journal and is run as part of the Grass10 campaign. The Grass10 programme has placed an ongoing focus on improving nutrient management and efficiency on farms, clover establishment and its management.

Applicants were required to have an established level of grass production on their farms prior to entering the competition. They were pre-judged based on past pasture production and nutrient management data, which included several key factors. These factors included total grass production (measured in tons per hectare), the number of grazings achieved, and average pre-grazing yield, and the level of clover content in the pasture. In addition, the judges considered the level of nitrogen (N) usage, both organic and inorganic, along with soil fertility data and the level of reseeding carried out on the farm. A strong knowledge of farm soil fertility was considered essential. The sustainability of the pasture-based production system was also assessed, and the competition placed emphasis on the necessary grazing infrastructure available on each farm.

1st prize winner //Patrick O Neill// //Low Chemical N/High Clover grazing System//

Patrick O'Neill's farm, a commercial dairy farmer, located in Firmount, Longford, had a total farm area of 74 hectares in 2023, with 64 hectares designated as the milking platform. The farm operated with an overall stocking rate of 2.0 livestock units (LU) per hectare and a stocking rate of 177 kg of organic nitrogen (N) per hectare. With 107 cows on the farm, Patrick produced 427 kg of milk solids. His operation focused on maintaining a very low cost of production, contributing to the farm's financial efficiency.

In terms of biodiversity, Patrick's farm was recognized for its high sustainability, featuring a high proportion of hedgerows and a substantial number of trees. The hedgerow management was exemplary, and the farm maintained a low level of herbicide use. Two high biodiversity habitats were

present, and a high level of protected urea was used, further demonstrating the farm's commitment to sustainable practices.

The soil type on the farm was medium to heavy, with excellent grazing infrastructure and very good clover management. There were 32 grass measures taken across the farm, with an average of 9.2 paddocks per grazing cycle. The total grass grown was 11,400 kg of dry matter (DM) per hectare, with an average pre-grazing yield of 1,240 kg DM per hectare. Nitrogen use was carefully managed, with a total of 152 kg/ha of nitrogen applied, 140 kg of which was chemical nitrogen. Phosphorus (P) was applied at 8 kg/ha, while potassium (K) was applied at 59 kg/ha.

A total of 868 kg of meal per livestock unit (LU) was fed, and 5% of the area was reseeded. The grazing season on Patrick's farm lasted 292 days. The farm's soil management showed an average pH of 6.45, with phosphorus and potassium indexes both averaging at 3. The Nitrogen Use Efficiency (NUE) was 32%, and there was a surplus of 112 kg of nitrogen. The clover levels were high, with 7% at a high level and 12% at a medium level, indicating the farm's strong focus on fostering sustainable and productive grassland management.

2nd prize winner //Killian Brennan// Extending the grazing season length//

Killian Brennan farms in Kilcogy, Co. Cavan with his wife Madeline and their 3 children. The Brennan's farm on a 34ha milking platform with 113 cows and have a 20ha support out block and all their young stock are contract reared. The farm has put an emphasis on improving soil fertility and incorporating clover over the last 10 years. White clover for the grazing paddocks and red clover for the silage paddocks is included in the reseeded programme on the farm. They have also spent money on upgrading and putting in cambered roadways to improve access to paddocks. They have also included astroturf on high volume areas of the roadways to improve cow flow and help reduce lameness. There are multiple access points to every part of the paddock and this has allowed the cows to have increased days at

grass on their farm.

3rd prize winner //Billy Gilmore// //Contract Heifer Rearing//

Billy and his wife Anne manage a contract heifer rearing system, raising over 200 heifers annually. The operation has evolved over time, transitioning from a mixed system that included an autumn-calving suckler herd, a spring-lambing flock, and a tillage operation.

In their current contract rearing system, Billy and Anne enter into written agreements with dairy farmers, where the farmer provides heifers to be reared at a predetermined daily fee per head. In return, the contract rearer is responsible for the care and maintenance of the heifers, ensuring they are returned in good condition and in-calf. The age at which the heifers are moved and returned to the owner's farm can vary based on the specific terms of the agreement.

On the Gilmore farm, Billy places great importance on gradually turning the calves and yearling heifers out to grass. He emphasizes the crucial practice of grass measuring to ensure the animals always have

access to high-quality pasture. This approach helps reduce reliance on concentrated feed, allowing Billy and Anne to primarily feed the animal's home-grown forage. As a result, they are able to lower input costs and run a more sustainable operation.

G4AE storytelling video award description

The storytelling competition was held at Teagasc Moorepark in Fermoy, County Cork, with each student creating his or her own video. The event was organized by the Facilitator Agent (FA) and supported by Teagasc. It aimed to teach students the craft of storytelling and video making. Participants were guided through two hands-on sessions, where they learned the essential techniques of both storytelling and video production.

On 6th February 2025, a seminar took place in Teagasc, Moorepark, Fermoy Co Cork, with 20 students from University College Dublin, focusing on storytelling and video production which lasted for three hours. The session began with students learning how to create engaging narratives and capture them effectively on video using their smartphones. The focus then shifted to video editing, where students explored the VN app, learning how to add features and edit videos.

Students from University College Dublin were tasked with creating a short video that showcased their own farm, providing them with an opportunity to demonstrate their videomaking and editing skills. The project encouraged creativity, with each student capturing various aspects of their farming practices, animal care or sustainable farming techniques. After completing their videos, the students submitted their work for evaluation. Three students were selected as finalists based on the quality of their storytelling, video production, and editing. The finalists' videos were reviewed for creativity, technical skills, and how well they highlighted key elements of farm life. From these three, one student was chosen as the winner. The student was recognized for his exceptional videomaking and editing abilities. His video stood out for its clarity, visual appeal, and skillful use of editing techniques, which effectively showcased the unique aspects of his farm.

5. Grazing4Agroecology Italy Awards

G4AE Grazing farm award description

The G4AE competition for Italy was held in South Tyrol and was organized by the project partners Laimburg Research Centre and Bioland Südtirol. Alongside the project partners, the region's leading agricultural cooperative "Landwirtschaftliche Hauptgenossenschaft Südtirol" was successfully secured as an additional sponsor for the award. The competition aimed to encourage grazing farms best fulfilling the 5 principles of agroecology to take part in it. The call for applications for the award was publicised through local agricultural media "Südtiroler Landwirt", as well as the communication channels of the project partners' network, including their website, newsletter and social media platforms.

In the period between April and September 2024, interested farms had the possibility to register using an online questionnaire in Google Forms, where they provided relevant data and a detailed description of how they implement the 5 agroecological principles on their farms. A total of 9 farms across South Tyrol took part in the competition. A four-member jury consisting of advisers, researchers and industry made an anonymous pre-selection based on the submitted questionnaires. The three best-ranked farms were then visited directly by the jury and the project partners. Following the farm visits, the jury then assessed the three farms again, assigning scores from 1 to 10 based on the overall performance considering the five pillars of agroecology. The final ranking was determined by summing up the individual scores given by the jury members. The winner was chosen by all jury members with a total of 27.1 points out of 30 points. The farms that reached the second and third place were very close, with scores of 24.3 and 24.1 points, respectively. The winners were awarded on January 31st during the

“Bioland-Seminar” held in South Tyrol, and were announced via the G4AE social media platforms and on a local press release in February.

1st prize winner //Christoph Tasser and Sabine Widmann// //Optimising farm management with closed nutrient cycles and direct marketing//

Christoph Tasser and Sabine Widmann – dairy farmer, Reischach, South Tyrol, Italy

The farm “Unterhuber” is an organic dairy farm located in “Reischach” at 950 metres a.s.l. in South Tyrol (NE Italy). The family currently manages 13 hectares of grassland. The family keeps horned grey cattle in an outdoor climate-controlled barn, which is designed as a compost bedding system. This barn system offers good living conditions, with ample space, fresh air and natural light. In addition,

the cows benefit from an extended grazing period on nearby pastures throughout the vegetational period.

Sustainability is a top priority on the farm, with a strong emphasis on feeding the farms own forages and maintaining a closed nutrient cycle. The cows do not receive any supplemental feed. The farmer also prioritises self-sufficiency by using the own wood and minimizing external inputs as much as possible. Biodiversity is actively supported through the creation of flower strips. The milk of the 14 cows is processed into a diverse range of dairy products, which are sold both directly at the farm shop and to local restaurants. This enables the farm to achieve remunerative prices for the own products.

2nd prize winner //Alexander Agethle// //Cheese production and successful marketing using local adapted breeds on extensive pastures//

Alexander Agethle – dairy farmer, Mals, South Tyrol (Italy)

Alexander Agethle and his family run an organic dairy farm at 1,000 metres a.s.l in “Mals”, located in in South Tyrol (NE Italy). Currently, they manage 12 hectares of grassland. The milk from their 13 local Tyrolean Brown Swiss dairy cows is processed into cheese and directly marketed.

The grazing management is challenging. The land belonging to the farm is highly fragmented, with small non-contiguous paddocks surrounding the farmstead. Despite the land fragmentation, Alexander drives his cows to the short-sward pasture early in spring. The farmer’s passion for seeing animals grazing is his motivation for undertaking the daily cattle drive.

During the summer months, the animals graze on a mountain alpine pasture. Throughout this period, the pastures around the farmstead are fertilised with compost and mown at least once.

Grazing also offers economic advantages for the farm, as it reduces the need for machinery. The animals feeding themselves, offering an economic advantage to the farm.

The family's commitment to grazing reflects their dedication to sustainability, as proven by the successful direct marketing of their cheese products.

3rd prize winner //Philipp Tavella// //Pasture on extremely steep slopes//

Philipp Tavella – dairy farmer, Wengen, South Tyrol (Italy), Aiarëi Lüch da Paur

Together with his family, Philipp Tavella runs an organic dairy farm at 1,550 metres a.s.l in “Wengen”, located in in South Tyrol (NE Italy). The 12 horned Simmental cows are kept in an outdoor climate-controlled dairy barn with compost. This system contributes to implement animal welfare. Despite the farm's steep 15 hectares of land, the farmer places great emphasis on utilizing it for grazing. Grazing not only optimizes land use but also prevents hay harvesting during the summer months. The animals are fed exclusively on forage, maximizing the use of the farm's own resources. For example, sawdust and biochar from the surrounding area are used as bedding materials. Also the existing old buildings are well utilised. Biodiversity is supported through initiatives such as planting fruit trees. Additionally the farmers intention is to implement agroforestry, adding significant ecological value to the farm. In addition to milk production, sustainable forest management is an important sector of the farm.

G4AE storytelling video award description

The storytelling and videomaking seminar, organized by the Facilitator Agent (FA) and conducted by CNR, took place in Sassari in two three-hour sessions. The first session, held on 12/04/2024, focused on storytelling and videomaking, while the second session, on 17/05/2024 focused on video editing with the use of the App InShot video editor. Nineteen students of the local Agricultural Technical Institute (18 in the second event), the Istituto ‘Pellegrini’ in Sassari, and two teachers (one in the second event) participated. Students learned the steps of successful storytelling and videomaking, worked in groups to simulate interviews, captured video clips using their smartphones and practiced editing. During the second session, students collaborated to create and edit a shared video. They also learnt to use the various features of the App. These skills allowed students to create videos showcased at a national event focusing on environmental topics (Globe). The videos are now available on YouTube ([Video microplastiche](#), [video ragazzi classi prime](#), [Video ragazzi InShot](#)). The FA invited students to send videos focusing on the activities on their farms, but currently no videos have been sent yet.

Beyond the seminar, the FA provided one-on-one videomaking training to farmers in the national farmer's network. To further support them, the project partners Laimburg and CNR created a training video about videomaking in Italian language to be uploaded on the project YouTube channel. Especially one farmer was very active in sending short videos and one of his videos was awarded with the following evaluation:

His work was recognized for effectively following storytelling principles, using the App to add simple subtitles reinforcing the images and highlighting agroecological pillars such as ‘reducing inputs’ and ‘animal welfare’ as well as his passion for daily farming practices and attention to grazing animals. He was awarded a batch of seeds of self-reseeding legumes.

6. Grazing4Agroecology The Netherlands Awards

G4AE Grazing farm award description

Methodology for the Grazing4AgroEcology award selection in the Netherlands

The selection process for the Grazing4AgroEcology award in the Netherlands was designed to identify and celebrate outstanding contributions to grazing practices and agroecology among dairy farmers in the Netherlands, with a particular focus on young farmers and students preparing to enter the agricultural sector.

Recruitment of applicants

The award was widely promoted through channels targeted at young farmers and agricultural students in autumn and winter of 2024/2025. Announcements were made in classes at Aeres University of Applied Sciences, shared across Aeres' network, and disseminated via the social media platforms of employees of the farmers association ZLTO and Aeres. This multi-channel approach ensured a broad reach and engagement. We were pleased with the response, which yielded a competitive pool of applicants, making the selection process robust.

Selection process

A jury of five experts from practice and science, representing diverse backgrounds in ecology, agriculture, and education, was assembled to evaluate the applications. Each jury member independently reviewed the submissions and ranked their individual top five candidates based on the farm's grazing practices in relation to the five pillars of agroecology that are used within Grazing4AgroEcology. While the criteria focused on these core themes, each jury member applied their own interpretation, reflecting their unique expertise. This diversity enriched the evaluation process. The final outcome was determined by averaging the individual rankings, ensuring a balanced and fair result.

Celebrating the winner

After the winner was selected, a video was produced to showcase the farm and innovative practices of the winner. This video highlighted the winning farm's approach to grazing and agroecology, inspiring both current and future generations of farmers.

This methodology underscores our commitment to recognizing and promoting sustainable farming practices among young farmers and agricultural students.

1st prize winner // Weitkamp V.O.F. // Grazing4AgroEcology in practice //

Located in Noord-Sleen, Drenthe, the Netherlands, Weitkamp V.O.F. is an organic dairy farm managed by Renske Weitkamp and her family. The farm operates with approximately 90 dairy cows, young stock, and additional beef cattle. By implementing innovative practices, the farm aligns with several pillars of Grazing4AgroEcology.

The farm promotes diversity by incorporating herb- and clover-rich pastures into its grazing system. These species-rich pastures not only provide high-quality forage but also aim to enhance soil health and animal resilience. Strip grazing, allowing 3,500 hours of grazing annually, ensures efficient pasture utilisation and minimises feed waste.

Weitkamp actively contributes to biodiversity through initiatives such as 'plas-dras' areas—shallow water zones that create habitats for meadow birds and other wildlife. The inclusion of semi-natural pastures for young cattle and the preservation of surrounding ecosystems further support biodiversity.

Non-invasive fertilisation methods minimise soil disturbance and optimise nutrient cycling. Additionally, the farm maintains sufficient land to manage manure internally, eliminating the need for off-site transport.

By prioritising moderate milk production, the farm reduces physical demands on cows, promoting longevity and fewer health issues. Their approach also reduces feed inputs, as cows graze extensively during summer without supplementary feeding for three months.

Through its commitment to biodiversity, sustainable grazing, and reduced inputs, Weitkamp V.O.F. serves as an exemplary model of agroecology in dairy farming.

2nd prize winner // Maatschap van Eijden // // Biodiversity - innovative grazing system and nature-inclusive measures //

Irene van Eijden operates Maatschap van Eijden, a dairy farm located in Leusden, spanning 25 hectares of loamy sandy soil. The farm is home to 55 dairy cows and a boarding stable with 15 horses, combining innovation, sustainability, and biodiversity in its operations. Milking is carried out using a DeLaval VMS300 robotic milking system, and during summer, the cows graze freely while still accessing the robot.

The farm has been recognised under the agroecology pillar of biodiversity for its innovative grazing system and nature-inclusive measures. One of the standout features is the creation of four water ponds across the pastures. These ponds not only serve as shelter and cooling spots for animals but also allow local ecosystems to flourish. The removal of some ditches and preservation of older trees enhances the landscape, providing shade for the cows and habitats for wildlife. Additionally, hedgerows and stacked pruned branches offer further refuge for small animals and birds, while a snake breeding heap fits seamlessly into the natural pond environment. The farm also boasts orchards with apples, pears, plums, and cherries, supporting both human consumption and feeding wild animals such as hares, birds, and insects.

The farm leads in green energy innovation, boasting solar panels that power the entire operation, achieving a net-zero energy balance annually. Modern electric equipment, including an electric raptor and shovel, further reduces the farm's carbon footprint. Plans are in place to expand the solar panel system with a battery, ensuring greater energy efficiency.

This blend of biodiversity and sustainable energy highlights Irene van Eijden's commitment to an environmentally friendly and future-proof farming model.

3rd prize winner // VOF Byvingaheerd // // Reducing pollution by optimising the biogeochemical functioning of farming systems and reducing the inputs//

Martijn Huijzer and his parents run the dairy farm VOF Byvingaheerd in Zeerijp, Groningen, the Netherlands. Their farm spans 70 hectares of clay soil and operates under conventional dairy farming methods. With a herd of 120 dairy cows, they maintain a milk production intensity of 15,000 kg per hectare. One of the key aspects of their farm is its commitment to grazing, ensuring 3000 hours of grazing per year, which is well above the average in the Netherlands.

The family Huijzer has been recognized for their clear contribution to the Grazing4AgroEcology pillar of environmental sustainability – reducing pollution by optimising the

biogeochemical functioning of farming systems and reducing the inputs required for production. Their farming system focuses on reducing environmental impact while maintaining productivity. Between 2020 and 2023, they successfully reduced ammonia emissions by 15% and methane emissions by 2.5%. This was achieved through targeted feeding strategies, optimizing crude protein content from 171 g/kg to 165 g/kg, thereby lowering nitrogen excretion.

Grazing – they practise strip grazing – also plays a crucial role in emission reduction. By maximizing grazing days and hours, they effectively reduce the need for barn-based feeding and manure storage, which are significant sources of emissions. This low-cost system aligns with their broader sustainability strategy, proving that efficient grazing management can lead to both economic and environmental benefits. Furthermore, the farm contributes to the Grazing4AgroEcology pillar of animal health through effective herd management, which has resulted in improved cow longevity.

Through these measures, the family of Martijn Huijzer demonstrates how dairy farming can adapt to modern environmental challenges while maintaining high animal welfare and productivity standards. Their farm stands as a leading example of sustainable dairy farming in the Netherlands.

G4AE storytelling video award description

National video award

Two Dutch farmers and four advisors/researchers attended the online EU video-training webinar in English, organized by ZLTO on 23 November 2023. During this webinar, the call was made to participants to create their own video and share it, using the #g4ae hashtag. One Dutch farmer did this and created a nice video about her new farmshop:

[Click here](#) to watch the video on their Facebook page

[Click here](#) to watch the video on their Instagram account

On 20 June 2024, ZLTO organized an in-person workshop “how to create a video” on a farm in Heukelom. Three young farmers and two farmers attended the workshop. Both the workshop organizers and the workshop attendees started to follow each other on their social media channels to stimulate each other to make videos. Videos can now regularly be found on their social media channels.

From these videos, ZLTO selected a winning video. This video was chosen because it applied several techniques we had practiced during the workshop. In addition, the topic of the video suited the project.

[Click here](#) to watch the winning video on his Instagram account

ZLTO also organized a second “how to create a video” workshop in Cordoba, Spain for the consortium partners of the Horizon Europe SPARC project.

7. Grazing4Agroecology Portugal Awards

G4AE Grazing farm award description

Last year, the 15th edition of the International Veterinary Hospital Muralha de Évora Conference once again hosted the Innovation in Extensive Livestock Farming Award, for its second edition.

This award was aligned with national and European priorities to promote innovation in the livestock sector and aimed to recognize the most innovative farms in four key areas: Environmental Sustainability, Technological Innovation, Profitability, and Animal Welfare.

CONSULAI and the Grazing4Agroecology (G4AE) project joined this initiative, awarding the winner not only a monetary prize of €1,000 but also an exclusive trip to Ireland in April 2025. During this trip, the winner will participate in a field visit, attend multiple workshops, and receive a TEAGASC certificate as part of the G4AE Prize.

To be eligible, applicants had to be legally established as either a sole proprietorship or a commercial company, actively engaged in livestock farming in Portugal since at least the 2023 grazing season. Previous winners of the award were not eligible to apply.

Applications were open until February 18, 2024, via an online submission form. The evaluation process was conducted by a selected judging panel, which included Nuno Marques (Revista Ruminantes), Carolina Ramos (CONSULAI), and Nuno Prates (Hospital Veterinário Muralha de Évora).

The award ceremony took place in Évora on March 1st, 2024, and was widely promoted through Jornadas Internacionais Hospital Veterinário Muralha de Évora, CONSULAI and G4AE websites and social media channels.

1st prize winner //Monte da Ravasqueira // //GPS Collars//

Monte da Ravasqueira, owned by Sociedade Agrícola Dom Dinis, was the winner of the 2024 Innovation in Extensive Livestock Farming Award, in Portugal, being recognized by using practices that contribute both to the pillars of animal welfare and reducing inputs. This farm is in Arraiolos and has 1 500 ha.

Dedicated to an agrosilvopastoral system, the farm integrates mixed cork oak and holm oak forests, cattle, stone pine farming, and traditional olive groves. Since 2022, the entire farm has been managed under organic farming, reinforcing its commitment to sustainability and efficiency.

Monte da Ravasqueira stands out for its strategic focus on genetic improvement of the Limousin breed, prioritizing maternal traits, skeletal balance, calving aptitude, dairy capacity, and ease of calving. A key challenge for the farm has been optimizing gestation periods, as extended pregnancies beyond 295 days have led to larger calves. By closely

monitoring these trends, the farm is refining its breeding strategy to enhance efficiency and productivity.

The innovation that earned Monte da Ravasqueira this award is its implementation of GPS collars and cattle monitoring systems. This technology provides real-time tracking of herd movements, improving

grazing management, animal welfare, and operational efficiency. By embracing precision livestock farming, Monte da Ravasqueira represents innovation in extensive livestock management.

2nd prize winner // Associação de Criadores de Bovinos Mertolengos// Rotational Grazing //

Herdade dos Souséis de Baixo, owned by Associação de Criadores de Bovinos Mertolengos (ACBM), got second place in the 2024 Innovation in Extensive Livestock Farming Award. Located in Évora, this farm is part of ACBM's broader activities, which include managing the Mertolenga Cattle Breed Studbook and overseeing three beef cattle production units.

Operations at Herdade dos Souséis de Baixo began in 2014, with two part-time employees responsible for farm management: a technical farm manager and an agricultural support employee. The farm's herd consists of 60 breeding cows, including 40 purebred Mertolenga and 20 F1 crossbred cows, alongside an Aberdeen-Angus bull. Covering approximately 100 ha, the farm operates exclusively through grazing, with calves weaned and transferred to another ACBM production unit for further rearing.

The farm's innovation lies in its rotational grazing system, achieved by dividing the land into twenty 5-hectare paddocks, enclosed with electric fencing. This method allows for longer pasture recovery periods and short, intensive grazing cycles, enhancing biodiversity and soil health. In this way, the farm actively contributes to the pillar of Enhancing Biodiversity.

The Mertolenga F1 Program guides the farm's strategy, maintaining Mertolenga cattle as the maternal line to maximize weaned calf weight per hectare in an environmentally sustainable manner. This approach strengthens productivity while preserving ecological balance, setting an example for sustainable beef cattle farming.

3rd prize winner //Herdade de São Luís// //Livestock Diversity//

Herdade de S. Luís, operated by Sociedade Agrícola Cidade Alves, secured third place in the 2024 Innovation in Extensive Livestock Farming Award. Located in Évora, this 700-ha farm follows a dryland agro-pastoral system under organic production. The farm features a diverse montado landscape, combined of cork oak and holm oak woodlands, supporting a multi-species livestock system. The farm raises four animal species: 200 cattle, 100 goats, 60 pigs and 100 sheep. Only the cattle are not purebred, while the remaining species belong to native Portuguese breeds.

Given the heterogeneity of the landscape, Herdade de S. Luís employs different grazing strategies, carefully selecting species that best utilize available vegetation. This approach enhances natural resource efficiency while reducing the need for pesticides and heavy machinery, allowing animals to act as natural land managers. The dynamic and adaptive grazing system not only optimizes forage utilization but also ensures soil health and animal welfare.

The farm prioritizes production efficiency in dryland conditions, using the right tools for its specific environment. It actively promotes native breeds, direct sales with a focus on production transparency, and the conservation of the montado ecosystem. By integrating diverse livestock species, Herdade de S. Luís demonstrates a sustainable and resilient extensive farming model that enhances both biodiversity and economic viability.

This farm was rewarded thanks to the work performed on the pillars of Enhancing Biodiversity and Reducing Inputs.

G4AE storytelling video award description

On May 24th, CONSULAI hosted a video workshop for 11 advisors and farmers in Lisbon, Portugal. The workshop emphasized the importance of video creation, highlighting that 90% of the information transmitted to the human brain is visual. Additionally, 40% of people respond better to visual elements, and our brains process visual content 60,000 times faster than text.

The workshop highlighted the advantages of creating videos, focusing on:

Storytelling: Videos provide a powerful medium to convey stories, making messages more memorable and impactful.

Increase Engagement: Visual content tends to capture and retain audience attention better, leading to higher engagement rates.

More Personal Experience: Videos can create a more intimate connection with the audience, enhancing the viewer's experience.

Enhanced Brand Awareness: videos can significantly boost brand visibility and recognition.

Participants were taken through the various phases of video creation, namely planning, pre-recording, recording, editing, and sharing. Each phase was discussed in detail, with a particular focus on the planning stage.

During this phase, the workshop emphasized the importance of structuring a video effectively: the first few minutes should capture the viewer's attention, followed by a clear explanation of the topic, and concluding with a call to action.

The workshop also addressed the orientation of videos, explaining that vertical videos are ideal for social media platforms, while horizontal videos are better suited for larger screens and not recommended for social media platforms, unless YouTube. Additionally, the rule of thirds was explained as a fundamental principle of composition to enhance the visual appeal of videos. Participants were also provided with recommendations on various apps and tools available for video editing, equipping them with practical skills to enhance their video production quality. Several farm applications were received in the G4AE storytelling video competition that are currently under assessment. Results will be available on the G4AE website (<https://grazing4agroecology.eu/innovations/infothek-video/>).

8. Grazing4Agroecology Romanian Awards

G4AE Grazing farm award description

The competition was organized for the farmers who incorporate grazing into their livestock practices (including cows, sheep, goats, horses, and other animals). We specifically sought farmers who, through their own efforts, have demonstrated one or more achievements related to the agro-ecological principles outlined in G4AE project. The competition was jointly organized between University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Cluj-Napoca through the Grazing4Agroecology project and UBM Feed Romania. UBM Feed Romania Factory <https://ubmfeed.ro/> is the largest independent feed factory in the, one of the most modern factories at European level. They sponsorship the travel of young farmers in the Netherlands and second and third price.

Competition description: The competition was aimed at farmers who use grass for grazing as much as possible in animal feeding; Farmers were asked to send a short video filmed with their phone (max. 5 min) in which they describe the main advantages gained from using grass – cost reduction; pollution reduction; animal welfare improvement etc. A tutorial about how to produce video & story telling seminar

were organized with farmers in several locations (see below). A brief description of the farm – geographical location; land use (pasture/arable); type and number of animals;

Period of conduct: February – September 2024: registration for the competition. October 2024: jury deliberation and announcement of the winners for the best Romanian G4AE farmer (1st prize to travel to Ireland for the GPA meeting, March 2025).

There was a special section for Young Farmers (under 40) within the competition! The prizes and the period of the competition were: February – April 2024: registration for the competition. May 2024: jury deliberation and announcement of the winners for the best young farmers in Romania (1st, 2nd and 3rd prizes). The costs for Winners were involved in the Young Farmers tour in the Netherlands.

Participants and celebration: The G4AE award competition got an important media coverage. At the end 10 farmers send their materials using an on-line form. A jury of experts (science; farmers and industry) selected the 3 young farmers winners and the 3 G4AE farm award winners. The first ones were celebrated in an event organized by the University and extensively promoted on-line (Leontina Gordon; Sorina Lar; Alexandru Oprisa;). The 3 G4AE award winners were celebrated on-line. For them a special event will be organized in the AGRARIA fair (<https://www.agraria-dlg.ro/>) in April 2025 to maximize its impact.

1st prize winner //Cristian Echim, Monor, Bistrița-Năsăud// Rational grazing in an organic system//

Cristian Echim is a dairy family farmer. He works 85 hectares of land, most of which is pasture and hay-meadows. The farm is located in the village of Monor, Bistrița-Năsăud county, in an isolated area. All of his land is certified or in organic conversion. He owns a herd of 150 Bălțată Românească cows, of which 78 are the milking cows, and produces 273,000 liters of certified organic milk per year, milk processed by a large local processor.

He was awarded on the Animal Welfare and Reducing Inputs pillars. The innovative element is the parceled grazing. Of the 50 ha of semi-natural pasture, 26 are grazed in a rational rotational system. The dairy cows and the young animals have grazing plots in different locations. The motivation for such management is to manage plots with the best production and quality of feed for dairy cows. Another motivation is animal welfare, the farmer motivating that animals raised in this way have a longer lifespan and a lower susceptibility to diseases. The rotation is carried out at time intervals that allow optimizing the quality and production of feed obtained from the meadow and reducing soil erosion. The plots have variable sizes depending on the quality of the pasture. To fence the plots, the farmer uses around 10 km of electric wires.

In addition to the benefits that this system has for domestic animals, it protects to some extent from some wild animals, which have caused great damage in recent years, especially the bears.

2nd prize winner //Lehel Kis, Vlaha, Cluj// Rational grazing to reduce inputs and increase meadow quality//

Since 2020, Lehel Kis has owned a small family farm in the village of Vlaha in Cluj County. He works 6.5 hectares of arable land to produce his own fodder, mainly alfalfa, and uses 22.8 hectares in a mixed way, both grazing and mowing. Lehel owns 20 beef cows of a traditional breed - Sură de Stepă, which he sells live for slaughter.

The desire to own a farm is due to his close connection with nature and the traditions passed down by his grandparents, but also the relaxation that this activity offers, as an alternative to urban life.

He was awarded on the pillars of Animal Welfare, Biodiversity and Input Reduction.

Extensive grazing is practiced on fenced plots in the first part of the year, and after the hayfields have been mowed and the grass has grown back, the animals have access and graze these hay-meadow plots in the second half of the grazing season. This practice helps to increase the floristic biodiversity in the meadows, but also the genetic biodiversity of the species by disseminating seeds from one plot to another.

The motivation for grazing was to reduce feed costs, reduce labor time and equipment costs, but also to improve animal welfare, which is reflected in the high quality of the meat.

3rd prize winner // Leontina Gordon, Galații Bistriței, Bistrița-Năsăud // // Pasture fencing to reduce staff costs and protect against predators //

Leontina Gordon owns a farm with her husband in the commune of Galații Bistriței, Bistrița-Năsăud county. They manage a pasture of approximately 80 hectares. Here, 300 Țurcana sheep, 35 Romanian Buffaloes, 30 Bălțată Românească cows, 7 donkeys and two horses graze. The milk they obtain from the sheep, cows and buffaloes is processed on the farm, obtaining different varieties of cheese. These are sold on the local market or directly to consumers.

She was awarded on the Animal Welfare and Reducing Inputs pillars.

Due to the lack of staff and the difficulty in finding them, the couple decided to enclose the 80 hectares with an electric fence. The main motivation behind the construction of the fence was to increase the safety and security of the animals. This was achieved by:

Predator deterrence: The fence served as a physical barrier, significantly reducing the risk of predation, especially from bears which are a prevalent threat in the region.

Containment: The fence effectively confined the animals to the designated pasture, preventing them from wandering and potentially straying into dangerous areas, encountering predators or causing damage to neighbouring properties.

Prior to the installation of the fence, protecting the animals required a considerable expenditure of labour. At least one additional employee was required to constantly monitor and supervise the animals throughout the day. This was crucial to mitigate the risks associated with potential bear attacks and to prevent the animals from leaving the designated grazing area.

The implementation of the fence not only improved the welfare of the animals, but also simplified the farm's operations by reducing the need for constant human supervision.

G4AE storytelling video award description

Three video making workshops were organized in different farm organizations (07.02.2024 – Somes – Aries Cooperative; 10.03.2024 – Spermezeu; Somes-Tibles Cooperative; 19.04.2024 – Agraria Fair <https://www.agraria-dlg.ro/>, the biggest farm fair from Transylvania). During the video making workshops farmers and advisors were taught how to do a video. The participation in the G4AE farm award competition was based on the videos prepared by the farmers after the workshops and the on-line available video – how to do a movie. A panel of experts analyzed the videos and the best one was promoted through the website – Lehel Chis from vlaha de Jos. (<https://grazing4agroecology.eu/innovations/infothek-video/>).

9. Grazing4Agroecology Sweden Awards

G4AE Grazing farm award description

The Swedish Farmers' Competition called Sweden's Grazing Masters opened the 1st of April and closed the 31st of August. The 15 participants were dairy, beef and lamb farmers. The farms are distributed from north to south and on the west coast and east coast of Sweden. The farms represented both conventional and certified organic production, with grazing on temporary grasslands as well as semi-natural grasslands. Some farmers used grazing and grasslands as added value, others as mainstream production. The submitted competition entries were comprehensive with many best practises. The winners were awarded in October at Sweden's largest agricultural trade fair Elmia, which attracts over 20 000 visitors. Representatives from Sweden's University of Agricultural Science and the Swedish Grassland Society handed over the prize to the winners. The ceremony was covered by journalists from various agriculture publications such as Nötkött, Husdjur, Jordbruksaktuellt, ATL, Lantmannen, Svenska Vallbrev and Land Lantbruk.

1st prize winner // Anna and Anders Carlsson at Skogsgård // //A well-defined grazing system//

Anna & Anders Carlsson – Dairy farmers at Skogsgård in Southern Sweden

Anna and Anders Carlsson run the farm Skogsgård in Southern Sweden with certified organic dairy production; 220 dairy cows and 20 foster cows. The farm has 400 ha whereof 60 ha semi-natural grasslands. Grazing is important. The farm emphasis on utilising the resources on the farm in an economic way.

Anna and Anders Carlsson have a well-defined grazing strategy with emphasis on cost efficiency, the farm has adapted breeds and the grazing system is evaluated continuously. Furthermore, Anna and Anders are good grazing ambassadors who are constantly seeking

to expand their own knowledge and actively inspiring both the agricultural sector and the society.

One of many innovations on this farm is making foster cows from dairy cows, that for various reasons, don't fit in the dairy production. The calves learn how to graze, parasites are managed and these animals fit in very well on semi-natural grasslands. Anna and Anders received the grazing award. They were awarded on the following pillars for agroecology: animal welfare, reducing inputs and preserving biodiversity.

2nd prize winner //Tomas Olsson at Norrby// //A well-documented grazing system//

Tomas Olsson – Sheep farmer, Norrby in Central Sweden

Tomas Olsson runs the farm Norrby in Central Sweden. The farm has 1000 ewes lambing in January and April. The farm manages 200 ha arable land and 150 ha semi-natural grasslands. The paddocks are grazed during high season by 3–4 groups of 150 ewes and their lambs.

In order to utilise the pastures optimally there must be a useful way of controlling and monitoring the grass growth in the paddocks. The key is to graze the paddocks in the right order and to gather knowledge and experience of how to use the pastures efficiently.

One innovation on Tomas farm is the well documented grazing system. A big map on the wall in the farm office displays all the paddocks. The map is used to mark out the animal groups. There is also a smaller version of the map for field use, containing reference information for each paddock. The grazing is also documented in an Excel spreadsheet where the paddocks are colour-coded.

Tomas is always looking for methods for a more efficient grazing management with influences from other parts of Sweden and abroad. Thanks to improvements the pasture production has doubled from 5 to 10 ewes per hectare.

Tomas is awarded on the following pillars for agroecology: animal welfare, reducing inputs and preserving biodiversity.

3rd prize winner //Martin Ivarsson at Köinge// //Two cuts between grazing//

Martin Ivarsson – Dairy farmer, Köinge in Southern Sweden

Martin Ivarsson in Köinge in Southwest Sweden runs a farm with certified organic dairy production with 100 cows and 200 ha arable land. Martin's goal is an optimised grazing management using as much grazing as possible and continuously improving the system. Concentrating the calving to the right time for maximum grazing is one of the improvements. Managing the pastures for maximum quality and fodder intake is another.

One innovation on this farm is improving the grazing system by harvesting two times between grazing. As the paddocks are cut twice between the grazing periods there are no ungrazed spots left in the sward and there's a much better animal growth.

Martin is awarded on the following pillars for agroecology: animal welfare and reducing inputs.

G4AE storytelling video award description

A storytelling webinar is carried out on the 18th of February. Invitation is sent to a defined group consisting of the Young Farmers Group and Partner Farms. The submitted competition entries are evaluated in terms of content, attraction and creativity. The winners are selected by the Facilitator Agents and communicated within the group of participants.

Consortium:

Contact:

Website	www.grazing4agroecology.eu
f	https://www.facebook.com/Grazing4AgroEcology/
t	https://twitter.com/HEurope_G4AE
in	https://www.linkedin.com/company/89048577/admin/
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